

Table: Supplementary Appendix, S2

Secondary calibration points used in this study.

Calibration	Date in million years ago (Ma)	
	Espeland et al. 2018	Chazot et al. 2019
Tree height - Crown Age of Satyrinae	54.07 (40.7-67.4)	54.43 (46.02-64.82)
Split between Morphoni and Brassolini	45.26 (32.4-58.4)	41.59 (33.63-49.89)
Crown age of Satyrini	42.63 (32.1-52.9)	45.78 (38.46-55.06)

Notes: The values in brackets are the 95% confidence interval of the mean ages taken from Espeland et al. 2018 and the corresponding notes in Chazot et al. 2019

Table: Supplementary Appendix, S3a

Prior dispersal rate scaler matrices used in the BIOGEOBEARS analyses for the constrained Model, M1

Biogeographic area		A	B	C	D	E	F	G
Saharan Region	A	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.75	0.50	1.00
Guinean Region	B	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.75	0.50	0.25	0.75
Congolian Region	C	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.75	0.50	0.75
Shaba Region	D	1.00	0.75	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.75	1.00
Zambeian Region	E	0.75	0.50	0.75	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Southern African Region	F	0.50	0.25	0.50	0.75	1.00	1.00	0.75
Ethiopian-Somalian Region	G	1.00	0.75	0.75	1.00	1.00	0.75	1.00

Table: Supplementary Appendix, S3b

Estimated dispersal rate scaler matrices used in the BIOGEOBEARS analyses for the constrained Model, **M2**. The scalar multiplier m^n (where $m < 1$ and n =number of regions separating the regions compared) was estimated by optimizing the BioGeoBEARS output for the loglikelihood. m was estimated at 0.052

Biogeographic area		A	B	C	D	E	F	G
Saharan Region	A	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.052	0.003	1.000
Guinean Region	B	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.052	0.003	0.000	0.052
Congolian Region	C	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.052	0.003	0.052
Shaba Region	D	1.000	0.052	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.052	1.000
Zambeian Region	E	0.052	0.003	0.052	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
Southern African Region	F	0.003	0.000	0.003	0.052	1.000	1.000	0.052
Ethiopian-Somalian Region	G	1.000	0.052	0.052	1.000	1.000	0.052	1.000

Figure: Supplementary Appendix, S4

Bayesian Maximum Clade Credibility (MCC) phylogenetic tree of *Bicyclus* and sister genus *Hallelesis* inferred in BEAST based on a concatenated dataset of 10 loci. Numbers at the nodes denote the posterior probabilities after summarizing 3,750 post burn-in posterior trees from the BEAST analyses.

Figure: Supplementary Appendix, S5

Comparison of three models of dispersal-extinction-cladogenesis (DEC) estimated using the R package BioGeoBEARS and the Bayesian MCC tree. The three models include: M0=a null model that ignores differential dispersal rate scalars between the defined regions with two constrained models that took into account the ease (or otherwise) of taxon dispersal between defined regions, M1 and M2 are constrained DEC models that took into account the ease of taxon dispersal between defined regions by applying a scalar multiplier to dispersal events between areas separated by other regions. They however differ by M1 having the scalar defined arbitrarily (as in Supplementary Appendix S3a). and M2 having the scalar multiplier estimated by optimizing the BioGeoBEARS output for the loglikelihood (as in Supplementary Appendix S3b). The best-fit model was selected based on LnL (loglikelihood). The pie charts at nodes indicate marginal ML probabilities for the estimated ancestral areas according to the model. Other abbreviations are denoted as follows: d, rate of anagenetic range expansion; e, rate of anagenetic range contraction; j, relative per event weight of jump dispersal (founder event) at cladogenesis.

Figure: Supplementary Appendix, S6

Frequency distributions of anagenetic and cladogenetic events counts from 1000 biogeographic stochastic mappings conditioned on the Bayesian MCC phylogeny, geographics distributions of taxa and the best fit DEC model. The best-fit DEC, M2 is a constrained model with the scalar multiplier for dispersal events between biogeographic regions estimated by optimizing the BioGeoBEARS output for the loglikelihood.

Table: Supplementary Appendix, S7

Temporal diversification dynamics *Bicyclus* as inferred from TreePar analyses. Best fit model (in bold) is determined by ΔAICc ; the difference in AICc between the model with the lowest AICc, wAICc (%); Akaike weight of each model expressed as a percentage and $P(\text{LRT})$: Likelihood ratio test (at $P < 0.05$).

Model	Constant birth-death	BD with one shift	BD with two shifts	BD with three shifts	BD with four shifts
# Para	2	5	8	11	14
LogLik	-285.08	-273.10	-269.10	-266.47	-264.36
$P(\text{LRT})$	null model	0.000	0.046	0.153	0.239
AICc	574.29	556.85	555.84	558.04	561.85
ΔAICc	18.45	1.01	0.00	2.20	6.00
wAICc (%)	0.00	30.41	50.33	16.75	2.50
Rate 1	0.140	0.020	0.015	0.007	0.006
Turnover 1	0.000	0.058	0.142	0.294	0.303
Shift time 1	---	1.5	1.5	1.1	1.1
Rate 2	---	0.166	0.107	0.067	0.062
Turnover 2	---	0.029	0.180	0.266	0.354
Shift time 2	---	---	15.7	5.4	3.8
Rate 3	---	---	0.394	0.039	0.092
Turnover 3	---	---	0.331	0.440	0.465
Shift time 3	---	---	---	16.8	9.1
Rate 4	---	---	---	0.333	0.058
Turnover 4	---	---	---	0.529	0.509
Shift time 4	---	---	---	---	17.5
Rate 5	---	---	---	---	0.206
Turnover 5	---	---	---	---	0.644

Note: Other abbreviations are denoted as follows: BD, birth-death; # Para, number of parameters; logLik, log-likelihood; AICc, corrected Akaike Information Criterion; ΔAICc . Parameter estimates are denoted as follows: Rate, net diversification rate (speciation minus extinction); Turnover (extinction over speciation); Shift time, in which 'Rate 1' denotes the diversification rate and 'Turnover 1' is the turnover, both inferred between Present and the shift time 1 ('shift time 1').

Table: Supplementary Appendix, S8

Temporal diversification dynamics of *Bicyclus* Clade I as inferred from TreePar analyses. Best fit model (in bold) is determined by ΔAICc ; the difference in AICc between the model with the lowest AICc, $w\text{AICc}$ (%); Akaike weight of each model expressed as a percentage and $P(\text{LRT})$: Likelihood ratio test (at $P < 0.05$).

Model	Constant birth-death	BD with one shift	BD with two shifts	BD with three shifts	BD with four shifts
# Para	2	5	8	11	14
LogLik	-124.18	-116.44	-111.63	-109.26	-107.14
$P(\text{LRT})$	null model	0.001	0.022	0.191	0.238
AICc	242.18	234.52	243.18	238.85	247.88
ΔAICc	9.04	0.92	0.00	5.69	14.21
$w\text{AICc}$ (%)	0.64	37.09	58.81	3.42	0.05
Rate 1	0.127	0.017	0.013	0.006	0.004
Turnover 1	0.000	0.249	0.163	0.341	0.374
Shift time 1	---	2.8	1.945	1.7	1.7
Rate 2	---	0.157	0.043	0.055	0.041
Turnover 2	---	0.333	0.758	0.662	0.729
Shift time 2	---	---	17.031	7.9	7.0
Rate 3	---	---	0.548	-0.098	-0.136
Turnover 3	---	---	0.503	0.911	0.895
Shift time 3	---	---	---	17.5	10.8
Rate 4	---	---	---	0.436	0.411
Turnover 4	---	---	---	0.684	0.824
Shift time 4	---	---	---	---	17.651
Rate 5	---	---	---	---	0.160
Turnover 5	---	---	---	---	0.722

Note: Other abbreviations are denoted as follows: BD, birth-death; # Para, number of parameters; logLik, log-likelihood; AICc, corrected Akaike Information Criterion; ΔAICc . Parameter estimates are denoted as follows: Rate, net diversification rate (speciation minus extinction); Turnover (extinction over speciation); Shift time, in which 'Rate 1' denotes the diversification rate and 'Turnover 1' is the turnover, both inferred between Present and the shift time 1 ('shift time 1').

Table: Supplementary Appendix, S9

Temporal diversification dynamics of *Bicyclus* Clade II as inferred from TreePar analyses. Best fit model (in bold) is determined by ΔAICc ; the difference in AICc between the model with the lowest AICc, wAICc (%); Akaike weight of each model expressed as a percentage and $P(\text{LRT})$: Likelihood ratio test (at $P < 0.05$).

Model	Constant birth-death	BD with one shift	BD with two shifts	BD with three shifts	BD with four shifts
# Para	2	5	8	11	14
LogLik	-157.91	-150.91	-147.55	-145.39	-143.47
$P(\text{LRT})$	null model	0.003	0.134	0.249	0.265
AICc	320.05	313.05	314.23	318.92	325.43
ΔAICc	7.00	0.00	1.18	5.87	12.38
wAICc (%)	1.84	60.98	33.82	3.24	0.13
Rate 1	0.143	0.027	0.006	0.004	0.000
Turnover 1	0.000	0.142	0.350	0.478	0.554
Shift time 1	---	2.568	1.422	1.232	1.154
Rate 2	---	0.171	0.120	0.036	-0.093
Turnover 2	---	0.089	0.203	0.486	0.539
Shift time 2	---	---	10.407	7.562	6.470
Rate 3	---	---	0.098	0.106	0.108
Turnover 3	---	---	0.524	0.544	0.626
Shift time 3	---	---	---	11.490	9.287
Rate 4	---	---	---	-0.055	0.057
Turnover 4	---	---	---	0.692	0.585
Shift time 4	---	---	---	---	12.304
Rate 5	---	---	---	---	-0.475
Turnover 5	---	---	---	---	0.785

Note: Other abbreviations are denoted as follows: BD, birth-death; # Para, number of parameters; logLik, log-likelihood; AICc, corrected Akaike Information Criterion; ΔAICc . Parameter estimates are denoted as follows: Rate, net diversification rate (speciation minus extinction); Turnover (extinction over speciation); Shift time, in which 'Rate 1' denotes the diversification rate and 'Turnover 1' is the turnover, both inferred between Present and the shift time 1 ('shift time 1'). The

Table: Supplementary Appendix, S10

Comparison of paleoenvironment-dependent diversification models for *Bicyclus* using 100 randomly selected posterior trees from the BEAST dating analyses. The best fit model (in bold) is determined by ΔAICc , the difference in AICc between the model with the lowest AICc and the others; $w\text{AICc}$ (%), the Akaike weight of each model, expressed as a percentage.

Factor	Model	# Para	logLik	AICc	ΔAICc	$w\text{AICc}$ (%)	λ_0	α	μ_0	β
Null	BCST	1	-282.74	567.52	9.00	0.49	0.2792	---	---	---
	BCSTDCST	2	-282.72	569.56	11.03	0.18	0.2878	---	0.0162	---
Time	BTimeVar	2	-277.92	559.96	1.43	21.70	0.2533	0.0452	---	---
	BTimeVarDCST	3	-277.92	562.09	3.56	7.48	0.2533	0.0452	0.0000	---
	BCSTDTimeVar	3	-282.70	571.65	13.12	0.06	0.2912	---	0.0067	0.1662
	BTimeVarDTimeVar	4	-277.90	564.24	5.71	2.55	0.2459	0.0625	0.0063	0.0563
Paleo-temperature	BTemp.Var	2	-277.20	558.53	0.00	44.44	0.1666	0.1613	---	---
	BTemp.VarDCST	3	-277.19	560.64	2.11	15.47	0.1603	0.1644	0.0120	---
	BCSTDTemp.Var	3	-283.13	572.51	13.98	0.04	0.2000	---	0.0022	0.0370
	BTemp.VarDTemp.Var	4	-277.10	562.64	4.11	5.70	0.1483	0.1792	0.0512	-0.1202
Paleo-atmospheric CO ₂	BCO ₂ .Var	2	-282.11	568.36	9.83	0.33	0.0540	0.0028	---	---
	BCO ₂ .VarDCST	3	-282.12	570.49	11.96	0.11	0.0544	0.0028	0.0002	---
	BCSTD _{CO₂} .Var	3	-287.04	580.34	21.81	0.00	0.1380	---	0.0400	-0.0446
	BCO ₂ .VarDCO ₂ .Var	4	-282.02	572.47	13.94	0.04	0.0515	0.0032	0.0278	-0.0243
Paleo-land plant fossil diversity	BPlant.Var	2	-284.26	572.65	14.12	0.04	0.1157	0.0091	---	---
	BPlant.VarDCST	3	-284.26	574.78	16.25	0.01	0.1159	0.0091	0.0000	---
	BCSTDPlant.Var	3	-286.05	578.36	19.83	0.00	0.1385	---	0.0000	0.0021
	BPlant.VarDPlant.Var	4	-284.26	576.96	18.43	0.00	0.1158	0.0091	0.0000	0.0034
Paleo-Carbon-13 isotopic level	B $\delta^{13}\text{C}$.Var	2	-281.07	566.27	7.74	0.93	0.0747	0.0783	---	---
	B $\delta^{13}\text{C}$.VarDCST	3	-281.09	568.45	9.92	0.31	0.0731	0.0772	0.0000	---
	BCSTD $\delta^{13}\text{C}$.Var	3	-284.50	575.26	16.73	0.01	0.1425	---	0.0006	0.0034
	B $\delta^{13}\text{C}$.VarD $\delta^{13}\text{C}$.Var	4	-281.07	570.58	12.05	0.11	0.0695	0.0783	0.0328	-0.0938

Notes: B, birth (speciation); D, death (extinction); CST, constant rate; Time.Var, time-variable rate; Temp.Var, temperature-variable rate; CO₂.Var, Paleo-atmospheric CO₂; Plant.Var, land plant fossil diversity -variable rate; $\delta^{13}\text{C}$.Var, Carbon-13-variable rate; # Para, number of parameters; logLik, log-likelihood; AICc, corrected Akaike Information Criterion; Parameter estimates: λ_0 and μ_0 , speciation and extinction for the environmental value at present; α and β , parameter controlling the variation of the speciation (α) and extinction (β) with the temperature or time.

Table: Supplementary Appendix, S11

Comparison of paleoenvironment-dependent diversification models for *Bicyclus* Clade I using 100 randomly selected posterior trees from the BEAST dating analyses. The best fit model (in bold) is determined by ΔAICc , the difference in AICc between the model with the lowest AICc and the others; wAICc (%), the Akaike weight of each model, expressed as a percentage.

Factor	Model	# Para	logLik	AICc	ΔAICc	wAICc (%)	λ_0	α	μ_0	β
Null	BCST	1	-123.35	248.79	1.42	11.68	0.1297	---	---	---
	BCSTDCST	2	-123.34	250.98	3.61	3.91	0.1306	---	0.0017	---
Time	BTimeVar	2	-122.50	249.31	1.93	9.01	0.1029	0.0367	---	---
	BTimeVarDCST	3	-122.50	251.63	4.25	2.82	0.1035	0.0377	0.0034	---
	BCSTDTimeVar	3	-123.34	253.31	5.93	1.22	0.1307	---	0.0019	0.0076
	BTimeVarDTimeVar	4	-122.18	253.45	6.07	1.14	0.1028	0.0556	0.0134	0.0318
Paleo-temperature	BTemp.Var	2	-121.54	247.38	0.00	23.71	0.0988	0.1153	---	---
	BTemp.VarDCST	3	-121.45	249.54	2.16	8.04	0.0867	0.1386	0.0870	---
	BCSTDTemp.Var	3	-123.02	252.67	5.29	1.68	0.1579	---	0.0035	0.0122
	BTemp.VarDTemp.Var	4	-120.43	249.95	2.57	6.56	0.0627	0.2633	0.0246	0.1092
Paleo-atmospheric CO ₂	BCO ₂ .Var	2	-122.21	248.73	1.35	12.04	0.0846	0.0018	---	---
	BCO ₂ .VarDCST	3	-122.21	251.05	3.67	3.78	0.0849	0.0018	0.0052	---
	BCSTD _{CO₂} .Var	3	-123.36	253.36	5.98	1.19	0.1334	---	0.0482	-0.0560
	BCO ₂ .VarD _{CO₂} .Var	4	-121.21	251.49	4.12	3.03	0.0661	0.0047	0.0382	-0.0096
Paleo-land plant fossil diversity	BPlant.Var	2	-123.65	251.61	4.24	2.85	0.1184	0.0030	---	---
	BPlant.VarDCST	3	-123.65	253.93	6.55	0.90	0.1189	0.0031	0.0021	---
	BCSTDPlant.Var	3	-124.06	254.76	7.38	0.59	0.1267	---	0.0000	0.0037
	BPlant.VarDPlant.Var	4	-123.48	256.03	8.66	0.31	0.1190	0.0036	0.0334	-0.0751
Paleo-Carbon-13 isotopic level	B $\delta^{13}\text{C}$.Var	2	-123.49	251.29	3.91	3.36	0.0662	0.0290	---	---
	B $\delta^{13}\text{C}$.VarDCST	3	-123.49	253.62	6.24	1.05	0.0677	0.0281	0.0000	---
	BCSTD $\delta^{13}\text{C}$.Var	3	-123.77	254.17	6.79	0.80	0.1278	---	0.0000	0.0046
	B $\delta^{13}\text{C}$.VarD $\delta^{13}\text{C}$.Var	4	-123.49	256.06	8.68	0.31	0.0670	0.0285	0.0026	-0.0260

Notes: B, birth (speciation); D, death (extinction); CST, constant rate; Time.Var, time-variable rate; Temp.Var, temperature-variable rate; CO₂.Var, Paleo-atmospheric CO₂; Plant.Var, land plant fossil diversity -variable rate; $\delta^{13}\text{C}$.Var, Carbon-13-variable rate; # Para, number of parameters; logLik, log-likelihood; AICc, corrected Akaike Information Criterion; Parameter estimates: λ_0 and μ_0 , speciation and extinction for the environmental value at present; α and β , parameter controlling the variation of the speciation (α) and extinction (β) with the temperature or time.

Table: Supplementary Appendix, S12

Results of paleoenvironment-dependent diversification models for *Bicyclus* clade II using 100 randomly selected posterior trees from the BEAST dating analyses. The best fit model (in bold) is determined by ΔAICc , the difference in AICc between the model with the lowest AICc and the others; wAICc (%), the Akaike weight of each model, expressed as a percentage.

Factor	Model	# Para	logLik	AICc	ΔAIC	wAICc (%)	λ_0	α	μ_0	β
Null	BCST	1	-156.76	315.60	6.94	0.88	0.1464	---	---	---
	BCSTDCST	2	-156.76	317.76	9.09	0.30	0.1464	---	0.0000	---
Time	BTimeVar	2	-152.72	309.67	1.00	17.03	0.0879	0.0922	---	---
	BTimeVarDCST	3	-152.72	311.91	3.24	5.56	0.0880	0.0923	0.0006	---
	BCSTDTimeVar	3	-156.75	319.97	11.30	0.10	0.1465	---	0.0000	0.0099
	BTimeVarDTimeVar	4	-152.68	314.16	5.49	1.80	0.0876	0.0950	0.0019	0.0024
Paleo-temperature	BTemp.Var	2	-152.22	308.67	0.00	28.07	0.0532	0.2220	---	---
	BTemp.VarDCST	3	-152.22	310.90	2.23	9.18	0.0533	0.2238	0.0032	---
	BCSTDTemp.Var	3	-157.02	320.50	11.84	0.08	0.1455	---	0.0000	0.0089
	BTemp.VarDTemp.Var	4	-152.18	313.17	4.50	2.96	0.0525	0.2286	0.0216	-0.3537
Paleo-atmospheric CO ₂	BCO ₂ .Var	2	-152.80	309.83	1.17	15.67	0.0407	0.0038	---	---
	BCO ₂ .VarDCST	3	-152.80	312.07	3.41	5.11	0.0410	0.0038	0.0009	---
	BCSTD _{CO₂} .Var	3	-156.93	320.33	11.66	0.08	0.1521	---	0.0025	-0.0338
	BCO ₂ .VarDCO ₂ .Var	4	-152.77	314.33	5.66	1.65	0.0401	0.0040	0.0237	-0.0287
Paleo-land plant fossil diversity	BPlant.Var	2	-154.72	313.67	5.00	2.30	0.1131	0.0146	---	---
	BPlant.VarDCST	3	-154.72	315.90	7.24	0.75	0.1135	0.0146	0.0007	---
	BCSTDPlant.Var	3	-156.95	320.36	11.69	0.08	0.1461	---	0.0001	0.0043
	BPlant.VarDPlant.Var	4	-154.70	318.21	9.54	0.24	0.1130	0.0147	0.0002	-0.0004
Paleo-Carbon-13 isotopic level	B $\delta^{13}\text{C}$.Var	2	-153.81	311.85	3.18	5.71	0.0143	0.1200	---	---
	B $\delta^{13}\text{C}$.VarDCST	3	-153.83	314.14	5.47	1.82	0.0153	0.1202	0.0023	---
	BCSTD $\delta^{13}\text{C}$.Var	3	-157.54	321.55	12.89	0.04	0.1444	---	0.0000	0.0040
	B $\delta^{13}\text{C}$.VarD $\delta^{13}\text{C}$.Var	4	-153.82	316.45	7.78	0.57	0.0143	0.1205	0.0601	-0.1385

Notes: B, birth (speciation); D, death (extinction); CST, constant rate; Time.Var, time-variable rate; Temp.Var, temperature-variable rate; CO₂.Var, Paleo-atmospheric CO₂; Plant.Var, land plant fossil diversity -variable rate; $\delta^{13}\text{C}$.Var, Carbon-13-variable rate; # Para, number of parameters; logLik, log-likelihood; AICc, corrected Akaike Information Criterion; Parameter estimates: λ_0 and μ_0 , speciation and extinction for the environmental value at present; α and β , parameter controlling the variation of the speciation (α) and extinction (β) with the temperature or time.

Figure: Supplementary Appendix, S13

Lineage-through time (LTT) plot showing accumulation of lineages over time in **a)** *Bicyclus*, **b)** Clade I and **c)** Clade II. On the right: Black lines are estimated number of lineages through time based on the maximum clade credibility (MCC) tree, which is overlain. The red dash line denotes predicted estimates based on constant pure birth rate. On the left, the dark black lines are estimated mean number of lineages through time based on 200 randomly selected trees from the posterior and the dashed lines indicate the 95% credibility interval across.

Figure: Supplementary Appendix, S14

Results of 20,000 mapped trees of ancestral habitat preference of *Bicyclus* implemented in the R package phytools using the 'make.simmap' function. The mapping was done using 100 replicates on 200 trees randomly selected from the posterior distribution of trees. The probability of habitat preference at each internal node (denoted as colour filled circle) reflects the probability of that node (i.e., ancestor) producing descendant lineages using the all rates different (ARD) transition model.

Table: Supplementary Appendix, S15

Results of the SecSSE analyses of diversification linked to species habitat preference. These analyses utilize the maximum clade credibility, MCC tree of the BEAST analyses inferred from 10 loci.

Model	# Para	Mode of Transition	Mode of speciation	Log-lik	AICc	wAICc (%)
CR ₁	3	Constrained single rate	Single inheritance	-363.16	732.33	0.00
CR ₂	3	Constrained single rate	Dual inheritance	-335.13	676.27	0.52
CR ₃	3	Unconstrained single rate	Single inheritance	-363.16	732.33	0.00
CR ₄	3	Unconstrained single rate	Dual inheritance	-340.54	687.09	0.00
CR ₅	4	Constrained openness	Single inheritance	-353.22	714.45	0.00
CR ₆	4	Constrained openness	Dual inheritance	-331.91	671.83	4.80
CR ₇	4	Constrained specialist	Single inheritance	-363.16	734.33	0.00
CR ₈	4	Constrained specialist	Dual inheritance	-335.11	678.22	0.19
CR ₉	6	Constrained four rates	Single inheritance	-350.70	713.40	0.00
CR ₁₀	6	Constrained four rates	Dual inheritance	-328.95	669.91	12.5
CR ₁₁	8	Unconstrained six rate	Single inheritance	-328.91	673.83	1.76
CR ₁₂	8	Unconstrained six rate	Dual inheritance	-344.54	705.08	0.00
ETD ₁	5	Constrained single rate	Single inheritance	-360.99	731.98	0.00
ETD ₂	5	Constrained single rate	Dual inheritance	-333.59	677.19	0.32
ETD ₃	5	Unconstrained single rate	Single inheritance	-360.99	731.98	0.00
ETD ₄	5	Unconstrained single rate	Dual inheritance	-338.82	687.65	0.00
ETD ₅	6	Constrained openness	Single inheritance	-352.93	717.87	0.00
ETD ₆	6	Constrained openness	Dual inheritance	-328.69	669.38	16.34
ETD ₇	6	Constrained specialist	Single inheritance	-360.99	733.98	0.00
ETD ₈	6	Constrained specialist	Dual inheritance	-333.59	679.19	0.12
ETD ₉	8	Constrained four rates	Single inheritance	-350.62	717.24	0.00
ETD₁₀	8	Constrained four rates	Dual inheritance	-325.74	667.48	42.23
ETD ₁₁	10	Unconstrained six rate	Single inheritance	-325.74	671.48	5.71
ETD ₁₂	10	Unconstrained six rate	Dual inheritance	-343.79	707.58	0.00
CTD ₁	5	Constrained single rate	Dual inheritance	-333.54	677.09	0.34
CTD ₂	5	Constrained single rate	Single inheritance	-361.05	732.11	0.00
CTD ₃	5	Unconstrained single rate	Dual inheritance	-339.62	689.25	0.00
CTD ₄	5	Unconstrained single rate	Single inheritance	-361.05	732.11	0.00
CTD ₅	6	Constrained openness	Single inheritance	-351.33	714.67	0.00
CTD ₆	6	Constrained openness	Dual inheritance	-329.19	670.39	9.85
CTD ₇	6	Constrained specialist	Single inheritance	-361.05	734.11	0.00
CTD ₈	6	Constrained specialist	Dual inheritance	-333.49	678.99	0.13
CTD ₉	8	Constrained four rates	Single inheritance	-348.37	712.75	0.00
CTD ₁₀	8	Constrained four rates	Dual inheritance	-327.99	671.98	4.45
CTD ₁₁	10	Unconstrained six rate	Single inheritance	-327.93	675.86	0.63
CTD ₁₂	10	Unconstrained six rate	Dual inheritance	-341.46	702.93	0.00

Notes: Parameter estimates and model performance in terms # Para = number of parameters, Log-Lik = log-likelihood, AIC = Akaike information criterion and wAICc (%) = Akaike weight expressed as percentage for of Constant-Rate (CR), Concealed-Trait-Dependent (CTD) and Examined-Trait-Dependent, ETD

Table: Supplementary Appendix, S16

Results of our SecSSE model validation using 30 simulated datasets generated using the parameters of the best-fit model. CTD and ETD refer to Concealed-Trait-Dependent and Examined-Trait-Dependent models, respectively.

Generating model	Inference model	
	CTD	ETD
CTD	25	5
ETD	1	29

Table: Supplementary Appendix, S17

Parameter estimates and model performance of different diversity-dependent diversification models inferred from DDD analyses for *Bicyclus* butterflies. Models are compared in terms of logLik, log-likelihood; AIC, Akaike Information Criterion; Δ AIC, the difference in AIC between the model with the lowest AIC and the others; and w_{AIC} , the Akaike weight of each model for constant-rate (CR), diversity-dependent shifting-rate (SR), and diversity-dependent key innovation (KI) models. For the SR models, the subscripts after the λ , speciation rate; μ , extinction rate; K , the estimated carrying capacity (maximum sustainable number of species), a proxy for the number of niches available for the group (or the number of species the group can sustain) parameters correspond to the diversification before and after the rate shift at t_d , shift time. For the KI models, the parameters with subscript 1 correspond to the main clade (*Bicyclus* Clade I) and those with subscript 2 to the subclade (*Bicyclus* Clade II). The key innovation is estimated to have occurred at T_d . Explanation of the CR models are: DI=diversity independent null model, DDL=speciation declines linearly with diversity and no extinction, DDL+E = speciation declines linearly with diversity and non-zero extinction, DDX+E= speciation declines exponentially with diversity and non-zero extinction, DD+EL = extinction increases linearly with diversity, DD+EX = extinction increases exponentially with diversity. df denotes the degrees of freedom in each model. ∞ *For these cases, the estimates were very large, tending towards infinity; the result is indistinguishable from a model with infinite K .

a. Comparison of CR model with Inf K (KI0) with standard KI models

Model	df	LogLik	AIC	Δ AIC	w_{AIC}	λ_1	μ_1	K_1	λ_2	μ_2	K_2	t_d
KI0A CR0 with dummy shift	3	-285.97	577.94	13.16	0.00	0.139	0.00	∞	---	---	---	20.2
KI0B CR1 with dummy shift	4	-278.73	565.46	0.68	0.23	0.256	0	138.0	---	---	---	20.2
KI1 Difference in K	5	-277.39	564.78	0	0.33	0.27	0.00	56.1	λ_1	μ_1	76.9	19.2
KI2 Difference in K, μ	6	-277.11	566.22	1.44	0.16	0.29	0.04	52.2	λ_1	0.00	73.0	19.2
KI3 Difference in K, λ	6	-276.89	565.78	1.00	0.20	0.23	0.00	62.2	0.31	μ_1	71.4	19.2
KI4 Difference in K, μ, λ	7	-276.89	567.78	3.00	0.07	0.23	0.00	62.2	0.31	0.00	71.4	19.2

b. Comparison of standard CR and SR models

Model	df	LogLik	AIC	Δ AIC	w_{AIC}	λ_1	μ_1	K_1	λ_2	μ_2	K_2	t_d
CR0 DI	2	-285.28	574.56	16.70	0.00	0.139	0.00	∞	---	---	---	---
CR1 DDL	2	-278.03	560.06	2.20	0.13	0.257	0	138.0	---	---	---	---
CR2 DDL+E	3	-278.03	562.06	4.20	0.05	0.257	0.00	138.0	---	---	---	---
CR3 DDX+E	3	-280.07	566.14	8.28	0.00	0.69	0.00	1.3E+10	---	---	---	---
CR4 DD+EL	3	-285.28	576.56	18.70	0.00	0.139	0.00	∞ *	---	---	---	---
CR5 DD+EX	3	-285.28	576.56	18.70	0.00	0.139	0.00	∞ *	---	---	---	---
SR1 Shift in K	5	-273.93	557.86	0	0.39	0.35	0.00	29.7	λ_1	μ_1	120.2	9.59
SR2 Shift in K, μ	6	-273.93	559.86	2.00	0.14	0.35	0.00	29.7	λ_1	0.00	120.2	9.59
SR3 Shift in K, λ	6	-273.82	559.64	1.78	0.16	0.40	0.00	28.1	0.33	μ_1	122.1	9.59
SR4 Shift in K, μ, λ	7	-273.17	560.34	2.48	0.11	1.19	0.15	21.7	0.32	0.00	124.7	10.24

Table: Supplementary Appendix, S18

Diversity-dependence diversification as inferred from DDD analyses for *Bicyclus* **a)** Clade I and **b)** Clade II. Abbreviations are denoted as follows: df, degrees of freedom; logLik, log-likelihood; AIC, Akaike Information Criterion; Δ AIC, the difference in AIC between the model with the lowest AIC and the others; wAIC, the Akaike weight of each model. Parameter estimates are denoted as follows: λ , speciation rate; μ , extinction rate; K, the estimated carrying capacity (maximum sustainable number of species), a proxy for the number of niches available for the group (or the number of species the group can sustain). Explanation of the CR models are: DI=diversity independent null model, DDL=speciation declines linearly with diversity and no extinction, DDL+E = speciation declines linearly with diversity and non-zero extinction, DDX+E= speciation declines exponentially with diversity and non-zero extinction, DD+EL = extinction increases linearly with diversity, DD+EX = extinction increases exponentially with diversity. df denotes the degrees of freedom in each model. ∞ *For these cases, the estimates were very large, tending towards infinity; the result is indistinguishable from a model with infinite K.

a) Clade I

Model	df	LogLik	AIC	Δ AIC	w _{AIC}	λ	μ	K
CR0 DI	2	-124.00	252.00	4.82	0.05	0.12	0.00	∞
CR1 DDL	2	-121.59	247.18	0	0.55	0.22	0	59.7
CR2 DDL+E	3	-121.59	249.18	2	0.20	0.22	0.00	59.7
CR3 DDX+E	3	-121.80	249.60	2.42	0.16	2.98	0.09	54.1
CR4 DD+EL	3	-124.00	254.00	6.82	0.02	0.12	0.00	∞ *
CR5 DD+EX	3	-124.00	254.00	6.82	0.02	0.12	0.00	∞ *

b) Clade II

Model	df	LogLik	AIC	Δ AIC	w _{AIC}	λ	μ	K
CR0 DI	2	-156.64	317.23	11.26	0.002	0.15	0.00	∞
CR1 DDL	2	-151.01	306.02	0	0.69	0.30	0	70.2
CR2 DDL+E	3	-151.01	308.02	2	0.25	0.30	0.00	70.2
CR3 DDX+E	3	-152.56	311.12	5.10	0.05	0.87	0.00	1.5E+12
CR4 DD+EL	3	-156.93	319.86	13.84	0.001	0.14	0.00	∞ *
CR5 DD+EX	3	-156.93	319.86	13.84	0.001	0.14	0.00	∞ *

Table: Supplementary Appendix, S19

PARTITIONFINDER2 estimated best-fit partitioning scheme and models of nucleotide substitution used for the BEAST dating analyses. The optimal scheme and models were selected using Akaike Information Criterion (AICc) corrected across all models included in BEAST (option models = beast).

Scheme lnL:	-64415.3194
Scheme AICc:	129672.1562
Number of params	399
Number of sites	7735
Number of subsets	21

Subset	Genome	Best Model	Sites	Infor	Invar (%)	Partition Name
1	Mitoch	GTR+I+G+X	492	413	8.3	COI_1
2	Mitoch	TRN+I+G+X	492	105	70.3	COI_2
3	Mitoch	GTR+I+G+X	491	22	86.8	COI_3
4	Nuclear	GTR+G+X	414	250	86.8	EF-1 α _1
5	Nuclear	TRN+I+G+X	1086	76	85.5	EF-1 α _2; GAPDH_2; ArgKin_1; MAD_2
6	Nuclear	TRN+I+X	1047	25	95.5	EF-1 α _3; GAPDH_3; RpS5_3; ArgKin_2
7	Nuclear	GTR+G+X	231	184	10.4	GAPDH_1
8	Nuclear	GTR+I+X	137	4	95.6	RpS2_1
9	Nuclear	GTR+G+X	137	113	6.6	RpS2_2
10	Nuclear	GTR+I+X	343	31	87.8	RpS2_3; RpS5_2
11	Nuclear	HKY+G+X	206	141	17.0	RpS5_1
12	Nuclear	GTR+I+G+X	138	93	22.5	Wgl_1
13	Nuclear	TRN+G+X	373	33	83.6	Wgl_2; IDH_3
14	Nuclear	K80+G	137	3	92.0	Wgl_3
15	Nuclear	GTR+G+X	198	124	22.2	ArgKin_3
16	Nuclear	GTR+I+G+X	284	178	13.0	CAD_1
17	Nuclear	GTR+I+G+X	283	38	76.7	CAD_2
18	Nuclear	GTR+I+G+X	520	29	88.8	CAD_3; IDH_1
19	Nuclear	GTR+I+G+X	245	164	14.7	MAD_1
20	Nuclear	HKY+I+G+X	244	7	89.8	MAD_3
21	Nuclear	HKY+G+X	237	151	16.9	IDH_2
TOTAL			7735	2184	62.7	

Notes: Properties (*Mitoch*= Mitochondria; *Sites*=number of sites or base pairs; *Infor*=number of informative sites; *Invar* (%)=percentage of invariable sites) of the suggested PARTITIONFINDER2 optimal partitioning scheme and models of substitution (*GTR*=Generalized time reversible; *TRN*= Tamura-Nei; *HKY*=Hasegawa-Kishino-Yano; *K80*= Kimura 2-parameter; *I*= Proportion of invariable sites; *G*= Gamma distribution, *X*=Estimated base frequencies) used for the BEAST dating analyses.

Table: Supplementary Appendix, S20

MODELFINDER estimated best-fit partitioning scheme and models of nucleotide substitution used in IQ-TREE for our phylogenetic estimation under a Maximum Likelihood framework. The optimal scheme and models were selected using Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) corrected across all available models in IQ-TREE, including the FreeRate model.

Subset	Genome	Best Model	# Site	Infor	Invar (%)	Partition Name
1	Mitochondria	GTR+F+R4	492	413	8.3	COI_1
2	Mitochondria	TN+F+I+G4	492	105	70.3	COI_2
3	Mitochondria	TIM2+F+I	491	22	86.8	COI_3
4	Nuclear	SYM+FQ+R3	757	504	16.6	EF-1 α _1; RpS2_2; RpS5_1
5	Nuclear	GTR+F+R3	1742	147	83.6	EF-1 α _2; GAPDH_2; Wgl_2; ArgKin_1; CAD_2; MAD_2; IDH_3
6	Nuclear	TN+F+I	2085	68	92.9	EF-1 α _3; GAPDH_3; RpS2_1; RpS5_3; Wgl_3; ArgKin_2; CAD_3; MAD_3; IDH_1
7	Nuclear	TIM2+F+R3	468	335	13.7	GAPDH_1; IDH_2
8	Nuclear	TIM+F+I	343	31	87.8	RpS2_3; RpS5_2
9	Nuclear	GTR+F+R2	336	217	22.3	Wgl_1; ArgKin_3
10	Nuclear	TPM3u+F+I	529	342	13.8	CAD_1; MAD_1
		TOTAL	7735	2184	62.7	

Notes: Properties (*Sites*=number of sites or base pairs; *Infor*=number of informative sites; *Invar (%)*=percentage of invariable sites) of the suggested MODELFINDER optimal partitioning scheme and models of substitution (*GTR*= General time reversible model with unequal rates and unequal base frequencies; *TN*= Like unequal transition/transversion rates and unequal base frequencies (*HKY*), but unequal purine/pyrimidine rates; *TIM2*= AC=AT, AG=CT, CG=GT and equal base frequencies; *SYM*= Symmetric model with unequal rates but equal base frequencies; *TIM*= Transition model, AC=GT, AT=CG and unequal base frequencies; *TPM3u*= AC=CG, AG=CT, AT=GT and unequal base frequencies; *F*= Empirical base frequencies; *FQ*= Equal base frequencies; *I*=Proportion of invariable sites; *G*= Gamma distribution) used for the IQ-TREE phylogenetic reconstruction analyses. The numbers after *R* and *G* denotes the number of discretized rate categories.